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Exploring the interfacial mechanisms behind enhanced performance of Si-based anodes coated with Al₂O₃

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of Al₂O₃ coatings on silicon-based anodes for lithium-ion batteries. We explore the mechanisms underlying improved electrochemical performance, focusing on particle interactions, surface modifications, and electrode characterization. Key findings include effective nanoparticle deagglomeration and enhanced adhesion through capillary bridges in hydrophilic coatings. Furthermore, Al₂O₃ coatings improve surface chemistry, Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) formation, and electrode topography. Additionally, they enhance mechanical stability and protect the anode from side reactions, leading to improved cycling performance. This research demonstrates the potential of Al₂O₃ coatings to mitigate challenges associated with silicon-based anodes, leading to improved overall battery performance.

1. Introduction

To address the escalating global energy demands driven by population growth and industrialization, finding safe, efficient, and sustainable energy sources is increasingly urgent. Rechargeable lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) offer a promising solution due to their high energy and power density, long service life, and low self-discharge rates [1–3]. Their widespread application in devices such as smartphones, laptops, and electric vehicles continues to drive research into advanced cell configurations and battery chemistries.

LIBs are primarily composed of porous electrodes (anode and cathode), separator sheets, and liquid electrolytes, which facilitate ion transport between the electrodes [4,5]. The porous electrodes not only host the liquid electrolyte but also enable the electrochemical reactions essential for charging and discharging [6]. The anode, in particular, stores and releases lithium ions during the battery's charge and discharge cycles, directly influencing energy density and efficiency [6].

Silicon (Si) is a promising anode material for LIBs, offering a theoretical capacity of approximately 4200 mAh g⁻¹ [7–13]. However, its commercialization is hindered by significant challenges, such as large volume changes (over 300% when lithiated), low electronic conductivity, slow lithium diffusion, and chemical reactivity with the electrolyte, which destabilizes the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) [14–16].

Surface coatings have emerged as a viable strategy to address these challenges [17]. Specifically, Al₂O₃ coatings have demonstrated the ability to enhance electrochemical performance by improving mechanical stability and reducing electrolyte decomposition [18–22]. The dry

coating method, which involves mechanically applying fine nanoparticles (NPs) to larger core particles, has proven particularly effective [23,24]. This technique leverages particle size differences to generate strong van der Waals forces, promoting the adhesion of smaller nanoparticles to the surfaces of larger, micron-sized core particles. Consequently, deagglomeration of the nanostructured particles is crucial to ensure proper adhesion.

Although Al₂O₃ has been extensively studied as a protective coating for silicon-based anodes [25–29], the interfacial mechanisms through which this coating enhances performance are not well understood. This study focuses on four key areas (Fig. 1): nanoparticle-nanoparticle interactions within Al₂O₃ aggregates, interactions between Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and Si core particles, both in the dry state and after electrolyte exposure, interactions between the active material and the other slurry components, and their impact on electrode topography and mechanical properties, and interactions between the electrode coating and copper foil, including those occurring during cycling (post-mortem analysis).

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is employed to measure forces between individual nanoparticles, providing insight into nanoparticle behavior, which is a key factor in the dry coating process. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), and Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis are used to characterize interactions and adhesion mechanisms. Peel tests were performed to quantify adhesion

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Fig. 1. Particle interactions considered in this study: (a) nanoparticle-nanoparticle; (b) Dry coating guest-host particle interaction; (c) slurry components interaction between themselves and (d) with the current collector; electrode surface morphology and (e) post-mortem analysis.

forces between the electrode coating and the copper foil. Post-mortem analyses, including X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) and SEM, assess the effects of different coatings on performance and cycling behavior.

By systematically investigating surface modifications and particle interactions, particularly focusing on Al_2O_3 coatings, this study seeks to advance the understanding of their impact on LIB performance. Through the integration of experimental and theoretical approaches, we aim to provide a comprehensive picture of these interactions and their implications for battery technology.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Sample preparation

Commercial SiO_x/C powder (HESO[®] from AMPRIUS) with an average particle size distribution of $16\ \mu\text{m}$ and nanostructured fumed Al_2O_3 (AEROXIDE[®] from Evonik Operations GmbH) were used. Two surface types of the nanoparticles were employed: hydrophilic (AEROXIDE[®] Alu 130) and hydrophobic (AEROXIDE[®] Alu C 805). Hydrophobic surfaces were achieved by treating the hydrophilic particles with organosilanes. Dry coating was performed using a lab-scale high-energy mixer (Somakon mixer MP-GL) from Somakon Verfahrenstechnik UG. The SiO_x/C powder was combined with 1 wt% of nanostructured fumed Al_2O_3 powder. Initially, the powders were mixed for 1 min at 500 rpm to ensure uniformity. A critical step was the deagglomeration of the nanostructured Al_2O_3 to create small aggregates that adhere to the surface of the active material through Van der Waals forces and mechanical mixing. This was achieved by increasing the mixing intensity to 2000 rpm for 6 min, and the resulting material from this dry coating process was used for further analysis.

2.2. Electrode preparation

The coated SiO_x/C powder prepared via dry coating was combined with Super C65 carbon black (CB, TIMCAL) and single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT, TUBALL[®] BATT H_2O 0.4%) as the conductive agents, and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC, Alfa Aesar) as the binder and water as the solvent. A slurry was prepared by mixing SiO_x/C powder, carbon black, and binder in an 80:10:10 weight ratio using a planetary centrifugal mixer (THINKY U.S.A., INC.). Electrodes were then fabricated by casting the slurry onto copper foil using a

doctor blade coater with a $60\ \mu\text{m}$ gap thickness. After coating, the electrodes were dried at room temperature for 15 min, followed by drying at $80\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min. They were then placed in a vacuum oven and further dried for 12 h at $110\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The active material loading was $2.2\ \text{mAh cm}^{-2}$, assuming a theoretical specific capacity of $1400\ \text{mAhg}^{-1}$ for the Si.

2.3. Sample characterization

Morphological and chemical characterizations were conducted on both fresh and cycled electrodes. Cycled cells were disassembled, and the electrodes were removed. The electrodes were rinsed in dimethyl carbonate solvent within an argon-filled glove box. Subsequently, the electrodes were dried overnight in preparation for structural analysis.

The morphology of the particles was investigated using a JSM-7600 F SEM from Jeol. The accelerating voltage was set to 1 kV, and the beam current was 30 pA. Samples were attached to the sample holders using graphite tape. EDX measurements were conducted using an X-Max 150 mm² detector (Oxford Instruments) and processed with Aztec software. For EDX measurements, the accelerating voltage and beam current were increased to 20 kV and 500 pA, respectively. Cross sections of the cycled electrodes were prepared by embedding them in an organic resin and subsequently cutting them via microtomy. Surface area measurements were conducted according to the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) theory. Three-point BET measurements were performed using a Micromeritics TriStar 3000 with a nitrogen/helium flow (28.6% N_2). Samples were degassed under vacuum ($\leq 10\ \mu\text{mHg}$) at $150\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min prior to measurement.

To characterize the interaction of the anode active material with electrolyte, the powdered materials (SiO_x/C uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of hydrophobized and hydrophilic Al_2O_3) were mixed with a commercially purchased electrolyte (1.0M LiPF_6 in EC:DEC=50:50 (v/v)) from Sigma Aldrich. This composition simulates the powder/electrolyte ratio used during cell assembly. To study the effect of Al_2O_3 as a coating, two additional samples were prepared with the uncoated material and the two grades of Al_2O_3 free-flowing, instead of coated on the surface of the SiO_x/C material. Additionally, to investigate the effect of Al_2O_3 as an electrolyte additive, two other samples were prepared with only the electrolyte and the nanoparticles — without the SiO_x/C material. The samples were prepared in the glove box and stored in glass vials, sealed with a lid together with parafilm to minimize oxygen and water exposure. After preparation, the samples

were taken out of the glove box to be stored in a 50 °C oven for two weeks. The soaked powders were separated from the electrolyte inside the glove box by individual filtering using filter paper (grade 3) and pouring DEC solvent to remove excess electrolyte. The powder samples were then put in glass vials and dried at 50 °C under vacuum overnight.

XPS measurements were performed on powder samples after interacting with electrolyte. Before measurement, the samples were evacuated at room temperature down to 10^{-8} mbar. XPS was also applied to cycled anodes in their discharged state. The cells were opened, and the anodes were cleaned following the procedure described earlier. The measurements were conducted using a ThermoFisher Scientific ESCALAB 250xi system, equipped with an Al K α excitation source. The measurement spot had a diameter of 900 μm . Depth profiling was achieved through argon ion beam sputtering at 5 keV. The graphite peak at 284.6 eV was used to calibrate the energy scale in the spectra, with a general resolution of 0.1 eV.

The apparent contact angle was determined using the sessile drop technique, which involves analyzing the droplet's shape to extract parameters such as the contact angle and base diameter. This was accomplished with the OCA35 from DataPhysics Instruments GmbH (Filderstadt, Germany), a device specialized in Optical Contour Analysis and contact angle measurement. Static contact angles on a flat surface were calculated with the SCA software, which automatically identifies baselines and tangents. Measurements were conducted with a low advancing rate of the droplet front, set at a dosing rate of 0.3 $\mu\text{L/s}$.

2.4. Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

To ensure uniform sample thickness, nanopowders were sandwiched between two glass slides and compressed. Adhesion forces between nanoparticle aggregates were measured using a Nanowizard IV (JPK) with triangular Si $_3$ N $_4$ cantilevers (DNPS from Bruker) with a spring constant of 0.14 N/m. The AFM was mounted on a vibration isolation table inside a noise isolation box. Force measurements were performed in air at room temperature with a constant relative humidity of 50%. Nanoparticle agglomerates were selected using a top view camera mounted on the AFM. Force curves were recorded using force mapping mode over an 8 x 8 grid within a 2 x 2 μm area. This procedure was repeated multiple times on different agglomerates for each sample to ensure statistical relevance and account for inhomogeneity. The applied force ranged from 2.5 to 5 nN, with a fixed cantilever speed of 2 $\mu\text{m/s}$ for every sample. The contact force between two single nanoparticles was determined through statistical analysis of the last peak in the force curves, as described in the literature [30].

2.5. Peel tests

Several 180 ° peel tests were performed using an Instron 3345 tensile machine with a 10N load cell, following the ASTM D903 Standard Test Method for Peel or Stripping Strength of Adhesive Bonds. Samples with a width of 2.5 cm were pulled at a speed of 50 mm/min.

2.6. Electrochemical measurement

CR2032 coin cells were assembled in an argon-filled glove box. The cells utilized a 1 M LiPF $_6$ electrolyte solution in ethylene carbonate/ethyl methyl carbonate (EC/EMC, 50:50 wt/wt) from Sigma-Aldrich. NMC 811 (Nei Corporation) served as the counter electrode, and Celgard 2500 was used as the separator.

Galvanostatic cycling was performed between 2.8 and 4.2 V vs. Li $^+$ /Li using a Maccor 4000 series battery cycler. A multi-step rate program was employed, starting at 0.1 C (charge/discharge) and increasing to 0.2 C, 0.5 C, 1.0 C, and finally 1.0 C/2.0 C every five cycles. Following the rate capability evaluation, the cells were further cycled at 1.0 C for 75 cycles to assess long-term cycling performance.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical performance

The electrochemical performance of SiO $_x$ /C electrodes coated with Al $_2$ O $_3$ via a dry coating process is significantly enhanced compared to uncoated electrodes. Fig. 2(a) summarizes the rate capability and Coulombic efficiency of both uncoated and Al $_2$ O $_3$ -coated SiO $_x$ /C anodes during charge–discharge cycling between 2.8 and 4.2 V vs. Li/Li $^+$. To investigate the influence of coating thickness on cycling performance, electrodes coated with 0.5, 1, and 2 wt% Al $_2$ O $_3$ were evaluated alongside the uncoated reference.

Among all samples, the uncoated SiO $_x$ /C electrode exhibited the poorest performance, with a discharge capacity of 444 mAh g $^{-1}$ and a capacity retention of only 43%. The 2 wt% Al $_2$ O $_3$ -coated electrode showed modest improvement, delivering 513 mAh g $^{-1}$ with 49% retention. The 0.5 wt% coated electrode performed slightly better, achieving 550 mAh g $^{-1}$ and 54% retention. In contrast, the 1 wt% Al $_2$ O $_3$ -coated electrode demonstrated the most favorable electrochemical behavior, maintaining a discharge capacity of approximately 736 mAh g $^{-1}$ after 100 cycles and exhibiting the highest Coulombic efficiency.

This clear performance trend highlights the critical role of coating thickness in balancing interfacial protection and transport properties. At 1 wt%, the Al $_2$ O $_3$ layer forms a conformal, nanostructured barrier that effectively stabilizes the SEI, suppresses electrolyte decomposition, and enables efficient lithium-ion diffusion. Thinner coatings such as 0.5 wt% may offer insufficient protection, while thicker coatings (e.g., 2 wt%) can hinder ion transport due to increased interfacial resistance and reduced electronic conductivity. Thus, the superior performance at 1 wt% reflects an optimal trade-off between electrochemical stability and transport efficiency.

The capacity degradation observed after approximately 25 cycles can be further linked to the specific cycling protocol. The multi-step rate test, increasing from 0.1 C to 1.0 C and 2.0 C, imposes progressively higher mechanical and electrochemical stress. Elevated C-rates induce rapid volumetric expansion of the silicon-based active material, leading to SEI breakdown and electrolyte degradation. In contrast, the Al $_2$ O $_3$ coating, especially at the optimal 1 wt%, provides both mechanical robustness and interfacial stability, mitigating these degradation pathways and improving long-term cycling performance.

Additionally, Fig. 2 presents the galvanostatic charge–discharge profiles of both uncoated and Al $_2$ O $_3$ -coated SiO $_x$ /C anodes at various cycles (3rd, 8th, 13th, 18th, 23rd, 50th, and 100th) under different current densities ranging from 0.1 C to 2.0 C.

The uncoated SiO $_x$ /C anode (Fig. 2(b)) exhibits significant capacity fading, particularly at higher current densities. This indicates a progressive loss of active lithium ions and a decline in the electrode's structural integrity, likely due to the volumetric changes associated with SiO $_x$ lithiation/delithiation. The large irreversible capacity observed in the initial cycles can be attributed to solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) formation and irreversible lithium-ion trapping within the SiO $_x$ matrix. In contrast, the Al $_2$ O $_3$ -coated SiO $_x$ /C anode (Fig. 2(c)) demonstrates significantly improved cycling stability and rate capability. The discharge capacity retention is notably higher compared to the uncoated counterpart, especially at higher current densities.

The subsequent sections will investigate the structural, chemical, and interfacial properties of the coated electrodes to elucidate the mechanisms driving the observed improvements in cycling stability and rate capability.

3.2. Dry coating process

The dry coating process was employed to modify SiO $_x$ /C particles with nanostructured Al $_2$ O $_3$. Dry coating is a solvent-free technique that utilizes interparticle forces, primarily van der Waals interactions, to adhere fine guest particles (Al $_2$ O $_3$) to the surface of larger host

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. Cycling performance of SiO_x/C uncoated and dry-coated with Al_2O_3 (average of 3 cells each): (a) specific discharge capacity and Coulombic efficiency; galvanostatic discharge profiles of (b) uncoated and (c) 1 wt% Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C , cycled between 2.8–4.2 V at room temperature at various discharge rates.

particles (SiO_x/C) [31–34]. The process involves high-energy mixing to overcome agglomeration forces within the Al_2O_3 powder and promote intimate contact between the guest and host particles. This results in the formation of a uniform Al_2O_3 coating layer on the SiO_x/C particles. Careful optimization of the mixing process is crucial to ensure efficient deagglomeration of Al_2O_3 while minimizing any potential damage to the SiO_x/C particles. By eliminating the need for solvents and drying steps, dry coating offers significant advantages in terms of cost, environmental impact, and process simplicity [23,24,34,35].

3.3. AFM force measurements between single nanoparticles

In this study, micron-sized SiO_x/C particles were used as host materials, and nanostructured fumed metal oxides were used as the coating material. These nanostructured particles were synthesized via flame hydrolysis, a process that inherently produces nanoparticle aggregates with strong chemical and sintering bonds. During the formation of fumed metal oxides, primary particles chemically bond, forming chain-like aggregates that can reach sizes of several hundred nanometers. These aggregates further cluster through physical interactions, leading to simple agglomerates typically measuring a few tens of micrometers, particularly during powder storage. Over time, these simple

agglomerates can merge into complex agglomerates, growing to several hundred micrometers in size [36–39]. To achieve optimal functionality, nanoparticles must remain as close as possible to their primary or aggregate sizes. This is also vital for the process of dry coating, as the size retention, combined with physical mixing, enables van der Waals forces to generate a robust adhesive coating layer [23]. Thus, the deagglomeration of alumina into smaller aggregates is a critical initial step to enable effective interaction with the anode powder surface during the dry coating process.

The energy needed for deagglomeration of alumina depends on the strength of interaction between the nanoparticles. In this work, AFM force spectroscopy was employed to investigate contact forces between individual nanoparticles in hydrophilic and hydrophobized nanostructured fumed Al_2O_3 . The AFM tip was used to penetrate agglomerates and isolate single chains of nanoparticles. Fig. 3 shows representative force curves for hydrophilic (a) and hydrophobized (b) nanostructured fumed Al_2O_3 agglomerates, along with a schematic illustration of the expected behavior of nanoparticles within an agglomerate during AFM force measurements (c–f) [39,40].

As the AFM tip approaches the agglomerate, it induces a rearrangement of the nanoparticles to accommodate the tip's presence. This rearrangement is reflected in the approach curve, where distinct peaks

Fig. 3. Force curves measured by AFM for the determination of the force needed to break up a bond between two nanoparticles for: (a) hydrophilic and (b) hydrophobized Al₂O₃. (c-f) The illustration of the mechanisms of the breakup.

appear following the initial jump to contact. Simultaneously, physical contact forces cause the nanoparticles to adhere to the AFM tip. As the tip retracts, these adhered nanoparticles form a chain that bridges the gap between the tip and the agglomerate. This bridging results in a complex unfolding process during retraction, which can manifest as peaks in the retraction curve (Fig. 3e) [30,39,40]. As the tip continues to retract, the chain eventually breaks at its weakest link. The final peak (Fig. 3f) is particularly relevant in the experiment, as it has been shown to correspond to the breakage of the connection between two individual nanoparticles, offering a direct measure of the contact force between them [30,40,41]. However, it is important to note that this method may involve more than two nanoparticles during the breaking event. To address this potential variability, around two hundred force curves were collected, ensuring a statistically reliable determination of the contact forces between individual nanoparticles.

Thus, the average force required to break the bond between two nanoparticles was measured as 2.64 nN with a standard deviation of 1.0 for hydrophilic and 1.01 nN with a standard deviation of 0.97 for hydrophobized Al₂O₃ nanoparticles. The higher force observed for hydrophilic nanoparticles is primarily attributed to the presence of a thin water layer (1–2 nm thick) on their surface, which facilitates stronger interactions via a network of water molecules [40]. This water layer enables the formation of capillary bridges between surface asperities, significantly enhancing particle adhesion. Capillary bridges can increase the adhesion force by approximately one order of magnitude compared to van der Waals forces alone [24].

Although hydrophobic nanoparticles also possess a water layer, it is much thinner and less cohesive, leading to weaker interactions. This difference in cohesion may also reflect variations in the coating quality between the two Al₂O₃ grades. The water-repellent surface of hydrophobic particles minimizes moisture adsorption and prevents the formation of liquid bridges, thereby improving dispersibility. As a result, hydrophobic nanoparticles are expected to achieve better coating homogeneity compared to their hydrophilic counterparts.

3.4. Characterization of coated materials

The SiO_x/C material, both uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of hydrophilic and hydrophobized Al₂O₃, was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy combined with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX). High-resolution SEM images at different magnifications of the uncoated (a, b) and coated samples (c, d: hydrophilic; e, f: hydrophobized) are presented in Fig. 4.

Upon coating, the SEM images reveal the successful deposition of alumina nanoparticles on the SiO_x/C surface without the presence of large agglomerates. This observation indicates that the dry coating process effectively deagglomerated the nanoparticles, resulting in a well-dispersed coating. Notably, the coating process preserved the integrity of the host material's structure, with no observable alterations.

Elemental mapping analysis revealed a uniform distribution of aluminum nanoparticles on the SiO_x/C particles coated with 1 wt% hydrophobized Al₂O₃ (Fig. 5b). In contrast, hydrophilic nanoparticles exhibited significantly poorer spreadability, as evidenced by uneven coating and the presence of localized agglomerates on the host particles (Fig. 5a). These findings align with the observations from the previous section. The hydrophobized nature of the particles minimizes moisture adsorption, preventing the formation of liquid bridges and promoting better dispersion.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of cross-sections of coated SiO_x/C reveal a unique porous structure (Fig. 6). Unlike traditional coating methods, the layer is not densely packed but exhibits a 3D nanostructured morphology. This porous structure, achieved through the dry coating process, enhances electrolyte penetration by providing interconnected channels and holes, significantly reducing the impedance of the Al₂O₃ layer [23,42]. Since the electrolyte's lithium-ion conductivity is significantly higher than that of metal oxides, the porosity can significantly reduce the impedance of the Al₂O₃ layer and ultimately lead to improved performance [23,42–44]. Since the porous structure of the Al₂O₃ layer allows it to absorb more electrolyte than a non-porous layer, it enhances lithium-ion conductivity

Fig. 4. SEM images of SiO_x/C : (a) and (b) uncoated, (c) and (d) coated with 1 wt% of hydrophilic Al_2O_3 ; (e) and (f) coated with 1 wt% of hydrophobized Al_2O_3 .

Fig. 5. SEM-EDX mapping of Al of SiO_x/C coated with 1 wt% of (a) hydrophilic Al_2O_3 ; (b) hydrophobized Al_2O_3 .

within the layer. This increased ionic conductivity effectively lowers the impedance of the Al_2O_3 layer, contributing to improved overall performance [23,42–44]. The porous structure of the coating layer was further confirmed by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area measurements. The uncoated SiO_x/C exhibited a BET surface area of approximately $1.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, whereas the Al_2O_3 -coated material showed a significantly increased surface area of $1.9 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The TEM images also suggest that hydrophobic particles (Fig. 6b) achieve a more uniform dispersion on the SiO_x/C surface than hydrophilic particles, which tend to agglomerate. This observation aligns with XPS and AFM measurements previously reported.

3.5. Al_2O_3 coated SiO_x/C interaction with electrolyte

To investigate interfacial reactions between the electrolyte and active materials without electrochemical processes, samples were stored at 50°C for two weeks [29]. XPS analysis was conducted on the anode active materials (AAM) surface after interacting with electrolyte to understand the chemical changes at the interface. Fig. 7 presents overlay plot of the Al 2p detailed spectra of the hydrophilic and hydrophobized Al_2O_3 coated on SiO_x/C .

Both spectra revealed the presence of Al_2O_3 and AlF_3 . The formation of AlF_3 can be attributed to the reaction between PF_5 (from LiPF_6 decomposition) and trace water, leading to HF, which further reacts with Al_2O_3 to form a passive $\text{AlF}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ layer [27,45,46].

The Al_2O_3 coating plays a crucial role in inhibiting HF accumulation and enhancing electrolyte stability through multiple mechanisms. First, Al_2O_3 acts as an effective HF scavenger due to its Lewis acid properties, readily reacting with HF to form AlF_3 . This reaction prevents excessive HF buildup, which could otherwise degrade the electrolyte and corrode the electrode surface. Second, the formation of AlF_3 creates a protective passivation layer that minimizes further HF interactions with the anode surface, preserving electrolyte integrity. This process, often referred to as the "HF or H_2O scavenging effect", has been extensively studied [47–49]. The reaction follows the equation:

Through this reaction, the Al_2O_3 coating neutralizes HF, thereby shielding the underlying anode active material from detrimental side reactions.

Furthermore, the AlF_3 layer contributes to stabilizing the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI). Unlike LiF , which increases interfacial resistance, AlF_3 has been reported to improve ionic conductivity and facilitate Li^+ transport within the SEI layer. This reduction in LiF formation leads to a more uniform and stable SEI, effectively lowering interfacial impedance and preventing continuous electrolyte decomposition [50,51]. Consequently, this enhanced SEI structure significantly improves the anode's electrochemical performance, including higher capacity retention, better rate capability, and long-term cycling stability [52,53].

Fig. 6. TEM images of cross sections of SiO_x/C coated by 1 wt% fumed (a) hydrophilic Al_2O_3 ; (b) hydrophobized Al_2O_3 .

3.6. Electrode topography

Electrodes were fabricated according to the experimental procedures outlined in the experimental section. Given the composite nature of these electrodes, it is critical to assess whether the 1 wt% alumina coating on the active material, which comprises 80% of the slurry, influences the properties of the final electrode.

To investigate the morphological effects of the dry coating process on electrode surfaces, atomic force microscopy (AFM) was employed to examine electrodes over a $1 \mu\text{m} \times 1 \mu\text{m}$ scan area. AFM provides high-resolution measurements of surface topography by mechanically contacting a sharp probe tip with the sample surface. This technique is particularly valuable for quantifying surface roughness and characterizing surface irregularities and morphological features.

AFM surface roughness curves presented in Fig. 8 demonstrate distinct differences in surface uniformity, with the hydrophilic-coated sample exhibiting minimal fluctuations, suggesting superior surface uniformity compared to uncoated electrodes (Fig. 8). While hydrophobic coatings exhibit superior dispersibility at the powder level, the hydrophobized carbon shell limits the adsorption of hydrophilic binders like Na-CMC during slurry production. In contrast, hydrophilic coatings promote better interaction with Na-CMC, leading to increased binder adsorption and improved slurry homogeneity [54]. This enhanced interaction ensures a more uniform active material distribution, resulting in more homogeneous electrodes.

(a) Hydrophilic

(b) Hydrophobic

Fig. 7. Overlay plot of the Al2p detailed spectra of pristine Al_2O_3 and coated onto SiO_x/C : (a) Hydrophilic and (b) hydrophobized.

3.7. Peel tests

In this study, the peel test was used to evaluate the adhesion strength of electrodes coated on copper foil. The test involves pressing the electrode onto double-sided tape, with the uncoated end of the copper foil clamped to the movable arm of the machine connected to a 10N load cell. As the movable arm peels the tape at a constant speed, the load cell records the force required to remove the tape from the electrode surface. A schematic of the peel test setup is shown in Fig. 9. The peel extension is defined as the displacement of the upper grip and the peel strength is the force divided by the width of the sample. This information is particularly relevant because the manufactured electrodes must endure several subsequent processing steps, such as electrode cutting, calendaring, wetting with electrolyte, and other mechanical stresses during cell operation [55]. These mechanical demands are especially critical for Si-based materials, which undergo extreme volume changes during lithium intercalation and deintercalation. These changes induce mechanical stress, particularly at the interfaces between the electrode components. When studying the mechanical stability of the electrode, it is essential to consider not only the adhesive force between the coating and the current collector but also the cohesive force within the coating and the physical and chemical interactions between the various components of the coating. Factors such as the size of the active material particles, the number of contact points, and the particle morphology all influence adhesion strength [55,

Fig. 8. Surface roughness curves obtained for electrodes manufactured with SiO_x/C (a) uncoated and coated with (b) hydrophilic Al_2O_3 and (c) hydrophobic Al_2O_3 .

Fig. 9. Schematic drawing of the peel test process.

Fig. 10. Peel strength-peel extension curves of anodes manufactured with different active materials (pristine SiO_x/C and coated with 1 wt% of hydrophobic and hydrophilic Al_2O_3).

56]. Consequently, the mechanical integrity of the electrode plays a vital role in the cell's longevity and performance [57–59].

Fig. 10 presents the recorded peel strength versus peel extension curves for pristine SiO_x/C uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of hydrophilic and hydrophobic Al_2O_3 .

When analyzing the interfacial strength between the coating and the copper foil, it becomes evident that the adhesion behavior varies with the type of active material surface treatment. The hydrophobic coating, for instance, demonstrates a peel strength of 50.4 N/m, which is approximately three times higher than the peel strength of the uncoated SiO_x/C sample, which is 18.5 N/m. Even more striking is the performance of the hydrophilic coating, which achieves the highest peel strength of 86.1 N/m, nearly five times greater than that of the uncoated material.

These differences can be attributed to the interaction between carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) and the SiO_x/C AAM. CMC exhibits strong binding properties due to its hydroxyl and carboxyl groups, which form hydrogen and covalent bonds with hydroxyl groups on the Si and C surfaces. This interaction is particularly robust with the oxide layer on the Si surface, leading to tight binding of Si particles together. Such strong binding helps maintain the electrode's structural integrity of the electrode material [60–62].

Additionally, the effect of coating SiO_x/C with Al_2O_3 on its interaction with CMC warrants attention. When the binder uniformly coats the powdered materials in the slurry, the average binder thickness on the particles increases as the total interfacial surface area decreases.

This increase in binder thickness enhances the strength of the electrode. The presence of Al_2O_3 on SiO_x/C increases the surface area and introduces numerous contact points, which facilitates polymer bridging. This bridging occurs both between the active material particles and between the solid particles and the copper current collector, leading to improved cohesive and adhesive strength [56,59].

Lastly, the interaction of CMC with hydrophilic and hydrophobic Al_2O_3 reveals that the hydrophilic coating yields higher measured values compared to the hydrophobic coating. This indicates a stronger binder-active material interface for the hydrophilic particles. The presence of a strongly hydrated boundary layer on hydrophilic particles increases thermodynamic stability by reducing the surface pressure of water on the nanoparticle surfaces, which helps prevent aggregation into larger units [63,64].

3.8. Characterization of cycled electrodes

To delve deeper into the structural changes of the electrodes post-cycling, cross-sections of the anodes were prepared and examined by SEM. These images were then compared to those of the electrode before cycling, as depicted in Fig. 11.

Post-cycling analysis of uncoated samples (Fig. 11a–c) revealed particle-depleted regions, especially near the separator, indicating that the intense electrochemical reactions in these regions may have led to the pulverization of the SiO_x/C material. In contrast, the Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C anode (Fig. 11d–f) cycled under identical conditions exhibited intact particles, highlighting the coating's protective effect. Additionally, the cross-section images of the coated electrode showed

Fig. 11. SEM of electrodes before (a, d) and after (b, c, e, f) cycling, manufactured with SiO_x/C uncoated (a, b, c), and coated with 1 wt% hydrophilic Al_2O_3 (d,e) at different magnifications.

Fig. 12. EDX mapping of Al of cross-section of electrodes manufactured with SiO_x/C coated with 1 wt% hydrophilic Al_2O_3 before (a) and after (b) cycling.

a porous structure attributed to the Al_2O_3 coating (Fig. 11f), further confirming its protective role against detrimental side reactions. The Al_2O_3 particles remained on top of the intact anode active material, as evidenced by EDX mapping analysis (Fig. 12). This confirms the stability of our coating layer not only during electrode manufacturing but also throughout the battery cycling process.

The solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer is a passivation layer that forms on the electrode surface during the initial battery cycling, primarily at the negative electrode. Its composition and stability significantly affect ion transport, electrode degradation, and electrolyte consumption. Optimizing the SEI composition and structure is therefore critical to improving LIB performance, cycle life, and safety.

To further investigate the effect of coating on the anode surface and SEI layer, XPS spectra of the surface of uncoated and Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C anodes were compared. The Li1s, C1s, O1s, and F1s spectra of both electrodes are shown in Fig. 13.

The Li 1s spectrum displays three core peaks at 55, 56, and 56.6 eV, assigned to $\text{LiOH}/\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3$, $\text{Li}_2\text{O} / (\text{LiF})_x(\text{LiPO}_3)_{1-x}$, and LiF, respectively. The $\text{LiOH}/\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3$ peak is only present for the SiO_x/C anode. LiOH is formed due to water contamination or degradation processes [65–68]. Li_2CO_3 is generally considered decomposition products of electrolyte components (like EC/EMC) reacting with lithium, leading to the formation of a solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) [65,69–72]. EC can undergo electrochemical reduction to form $(\text{CH}_2\text{OCO}_2\text{Li})_2$ and Li_2CO_3 [73]:

The higher content of Li_2CO_3 or $(\text{CH}_2\text{OCO}_2\text{Li})_2$ depends on the concentration of EC. High and low relative concentrations of EC result in the formation of lithium carbonate and lithium ethylene dicarbonate, respectively [74]. Additionally, Li_2CO_3 can be reduced to lithium carbide (Li_2C_2) and lithium oxide (Li_2O) when copper is used as the current collector [69,75,76]. An additional possible origin for Li_2O can be the degradation of Li_2CO_3 during Ar^+ sputtering in the XPS experiment [65,77–80]. Li_2O is predominantly ion conducting, even though its conductivity is so low that it may never serve as electrolyte in practice [81].

Lithium fluoride (LiF) was only detected on the surface of the Al_2O_3 -coated anode. LiF is thermally and chemically stable and not only suppresses electrode/electrolyte side reactions, such as LiPF_6 or carbonate decomposition, while enhancing the uniformity of the solid-electrolyte interface (SEI) layer but also enables fast lithium-ion transport at the interface between the electrode and electrolyte [65,69,82,83]. Moreover, LiF is known for its high mechanical strength and ionic conductivity,

Fig. 13. Overlay plot of the (a) Li 1s, (b) C 1s, (c) O 1s and (d) F 1s detailed spectra of cycled electrodes containing SiO_x/C uncoated and coated with Al₂O₃.

which plays a critical role in ensuring the SEI's durability. The high shear modulus of LiF (55.14 GPa) makes it an important compound of SEI to better withstand the significant volume changes associated with silicon-based anodes [73,84]. Thus, LiF-rich SEI layers have been linked to improved cycling stability and enhanced ionic transport, which can directly boost battery performance [85,86].

The presence of LiF is further confirmed by the F 1s spectra, with peaks at 684.6–684.9 eV. Additionally, the signals at 56.7 eV in the Li 1s spectrum and at 686.0 eV in the F 1s spectrum are attributed to decomposition products of LiPF₆ such as Li_xPF_y/Li_xPO_yF_z [87,88].

The C1s XPS spectrum is complex due to contributions from multiple components, including electrolyte solvents, carbonaceous SEI species, polymeric binder, and carbon additive. A prominent peak at ≈284.6 eV, observed for both electrodes, is attributed to C–C bonds in SuperP moieties [73]. Moreover, it is also likely associated with alkane and alkyl groups in the diverse SEI functionalities on the lithiated Si surface [73,89]. The peaks at 286.5 eV and 288.3 eV are possibly related to C–O and C=O environments in the CMC binder. The presence of carbonates, indicated by the 289.6 eV peaks, confirms the existence of Li₂CO₃. While detected in both samples, the carbonate peak intensity is significantly higher in the uncoated sample (41%) compared to the coated one (8%).

The O1s core peaks at ≈531.8 eV and ≈533 eV can be attributed to C=O, C–O–C (only in the coated sample), and –OH groups, respectively. These functionalities are associated with the binder material. As with the C 1s spectrum, higher intensity in the coated sample suggests that Al₂O₃ helps preserve binder integrity.

In conclusion, the XPS analysis reveals that the hydrophilic Al₂O₃ coating significantly enhances the surface chemistry and SEI formation on the electrode, leading to improved electrochemical performance.

4. Conclusion

This study offers valuable insights into the critical role of Al₂O₃ coatings in enhancing the performance of silicon-based anodes for lithium-ion batteries. Through a comprehensive investigation of particle interactions, surface modifications, and electrode characterization, we elucidated the mechanisms underlying the improved electrochemical performance achieved with these coatings.

Electrochemical cycling tests revealed a significant enhancement in cycling stability for the Al₂O₃-coated SiO_x/C anode, with a capacity retention of approximately 736 mAh g⁻¹ after 100 cycles, compared to only 444 mAh g⁻¹ for the uncoated electrode. This improvement can be attributed to several factors. Key findings include the effective deagglomeration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles during the dry coating process, enabling strong adhesion to the SiO_x/C host material. Hydrophilic coatings exhibit enhanced adhesion due to capillary bridge formation, whereas hydrophobic coatings demonstrate superior dispersion and resistance to agglomeration. Additionally, Al₂O₃ coatings significantly improve the surface chemistry and SEI formation on the electrode, leading to enhanced ion transport and reduced electrolyte decomposition. Hydrophilic coatings exhibit better wettability and improved electrode topography.

Furthermore, the presence of Al₂O₃ coatings enhances the mechanical stability and structural integrity of electrodes, as evidenced by

peel tests and AFM analysis. The coating effectively protects the anode material from detrimental side reactions, leading to improved cycling performance.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the potential of Al_2O_3 coatings to address the challenges associated with silicon-based anodes, paving the way for their widespread adoption in high-performance lithium-ion batteries. Future studies could explore the optimization of coating parameters, the development of novel coating materials, and the integration of these coatings with other advanced technologies to further enhance battery performance and durability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana L. Azevedo Costa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniel Esken:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Tatiana Gambaryan-Roisman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Frank Menzel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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